

Supplemental Table 3 (S3)

Sensitivity and specificity of nuclear markers ME, 18S, and 24S α individually for five vector species. All triatomines¹ includes in addition to all five species' specimens, 3 *Panstrongylus rufotuberculatus* and 44 non-genotyped *T. dimidiata*. [confidence interval > 95%, CI]. Bonferroni adjusted significance for χ^2 frequencies in bold: greater than expected: * = $p < 0.01$; *** = $p < 0.0001$; lower: †† = $p < 0.001$; ††† = $p < 0.0001$.

	ME sensitivity % (N) [CI]	ME specificity % (N) [CI]	18S sensitivity % (N) [CI]	18S specificity % (N) [CI]	24S α sensitivity % (N) [CI]	24S α specificity % (N) [CI]
<i>T. dimidiata</i> Hg1	84.0 (25) [69.6 - 98.4]	87.5 (24) [74.3 - 100.0]	48.0* (25) [28.4 - 67.6]	92.3 (13) [77.8 - 100.0]	12.0 (25) [0.0 - 25.4]	60.0 (5) [17.1 - 100.0]
<i>T. dimidiata</i> Hg2	87.8 (74) [80.4 - 95.3]	90.3 (72) [83.4 - 97.1]	28.4 (74) [18.1 - 38.7]	87.5 (24) [74.3 - 100.0]	20.3* (74) [11.1 - 29.4]	100.0 (15)
<i>T. dimidiata</i> Hg3	50.0 (10) [19.0 - 81.0]	100.0*** (5)	40.0 (10) [9.6 - 70.4]	100.0 (4)	0.0 (10)	- (0)
<i>T. pallidipennis</i>	72.8 (114) [66.3 - 79.3]	83.0 (100) [75.6 - 90.4]	8.8†† (114) [3.6 - 14.0]	66.7 (15) [42.8 - 90.5]	0.0††† (114)	- (0)
<i>T. phyllosoma</i>	73.9 (23) [56.0 - 91.9]	100.0 (17)	13.0 (23) [0.0 - 26.7]	60.0 (5) [17.1 - 100.0]	0.0 (23)	- (0)
All triatomines ¹	77.1 (293) [72.3 - 81.9]	85.9 (263) [81.7 - 90.1]	23.5 (293) [18.7 - 28.4]	86.3 (80) [78.7 - 93.8]	9.9 (293) [6.5 - 13.3]	85.3 (34) [73.4 - 97.2]